

INFLUENCE OF SAQ TRAINING ON SPEED AND AGILITY AMONG GRASSROOTS VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS

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Abstract:

This study was designed to investigate the influence of SAQ training on speed and agility among grassroots volleyball players. To achieve the purpose of the study 30 grassroots volleyball players were selected from Sacred College, Thevara, Kerala. The selected subjects were randomly assigned to two equal groups (n=15). Group- I underwent SAQ training and it is called as SAQ Training Group (SAQTG) and Group - II act as a control group (CG). The respective SAQ training was given to the SAQTG for 3 days per week (Monday, Wednesday and Friday) the period of twelve weeks. The control group was not be given any sort of training except their routine. The speed was measured by 50-meter dash and agility was measured by 4 x 10 shuttle run test. The data collected from the subjects was statistically analyzed with 't' ratio to find out significant improvement if any at 0.05 level of confidence. The results of this study indicated that the influence of SAQ training significantly changes over the speed and agility of grassroots volleyball players.

Key Words: SAQ Training, Speed, Agility and Grassroots Volleyball Players.

Introduction:

The SAQ training method more frequently uses the programmed than random type conditioning after the SAQ continuum. One SAQ session is composed of 7 components, where the main part of the session, explosion and expression of potential, are combinations of programmed and random conditioning. Integral planning and programming are required to progress from fundamental movement patterns to highly positional specific movements a logical sequence in the learning process must not be neglected because it develops neural structures that are a prerequisite for elite-level upgrade. Onsequent, elite players manipulate with their bodies without the loss of speed, balance, strength, and control. Also, with correct movement patterns (technique) and greater muscle power, they accelerate faster.

First let me point out that of the speed, agility and anticipation components would most certainly be anticipation and to coach this most would agree is extremely difficult. So let us then focus on what we can improve through technique and training, that being speed and agility.

When considering speed more often than not we consider maximal speed and acceleration and ultimately the goal of speed training is to get an individual to achieve maximum speed in as short a time as possible. This is obviously achieved through optimizing acceleration and is usually reached after a sprint acceleration phase of approximately 30 - 50m. Bearing that in mind it is likely that you may get the opportunity while attacker going to attack the ball the players need speed and explosive power. Our training interventions from a speed and agility point of view the volleyball players need to target acceleration because volleyball involves many bursts of explosive acceleration and linear distances in volleyball are carried out over mostly 2 - 5 m distances. The first and most important step in improving speed is to improve efficiency and we do this by improving running technique. This can be achieved through a basic understanding of technique and then the implementation of various technical drills involving apparatus such as hurdles, speed resistors and speed parachutes.

Most importantly we need to implement interventions focused on improving agility. This is achieved through drills that target foot movement and body position because these 2 factors will decide how quickly we change direction. If we can improve the speed at which our feet move, we can improve the time it takes to move towards the ball or between the blockers. As part of my training sessions, I will use ladders, hurdles and slalom poles to improve quickness and body position. The final step in the progression will see the introduction of moving stimuli such as passing or defending to ensure that the movements are relative to those that take place on the volleyball court of play and encourage reaction time and eye, foot and hand co-ordination. A part of all of us wants to be the one who takes that brilliant attacking, blocking that vital role or steals the winning of a person to win the game in volleyball. Through an understanding of the basic principles of speed and agility and the implementation of various basic training drills we can all improve how quickly we move and ultimately have a large role to play in both our personal success and the team's success as a whole.

Materials and Methodology:

This study was designed to investigate the influence of SAQ training on speed and agility among grassroots volleyball players. To achieve the purpose of the study 30 grassroots volleyball players were selected from Sacred College, Thevara, Kerala. The selected subjects were randomly assigned to two equal groups (n=15). Group- I underwent SAQ training (SAQTG) and Group - II act as a control group (CG). The respective SAQ training was given to the experimental groups for 3 days per week (Monday, Wednesday and Friday) the period of twelve weeks. The control group was not be given any sort of training except their routine.

Table 1: Criterion Measures

Variables	Test Items	Unit of Measurements
Speed	50-meter dash	In second
Agility	4x10-meter shuttle run	In second

Training Programme:

The training programme was lasted for 45 minutes for session in a day, 3 days in a week for a period of 12 weeks duration. These 45 minutes included 10 minutes warm up, 25 minutes SAQ training and 10 minutes warm down. Every three weeks of training 5% of intensity of load was increased from 60% to 75% of work load. The volume of SAQ training is prescribed based on the number of sets and repetition. The equivalent in SAQ training is the length of the time each action is held for and the number action in total 3 day per week.

Table 2: Computation of t Ratio on Speed and Agility of SAQ Training Group (SAQTG) and Control Group (CG)

SAQ Training Group (SAQTG)							
Variables		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference	Std. Error Mean	T Ratio
Speed	Pre Test	7.8600	15	.61737	.25067	.07008	3.57*
	Post Test	7.6093	15	.58790			
Agility	Pre Test	16.0620	15	.19380	0.07	0.02	3.85*
	Post Test	15.9827	15	.21107			
Control Group (CG)							
Speed	Pre Test	7.7533	15	.57553	0.02	0.02	1.00
	Post Test	7.7733	15	.57875			
Agility	Pre Test	16.1020	15	.22059	0.002	0.02	0.09
	Post Test	16.1047	15	.21437			

* Significant level 0.05 level (degree of freedom 2,14,1 and 14)

Table 2 reveals the computation of mean, standard deviation and ‘t’ ratio on speed and agility of SAQ training group. The obtained ‘t’ value on speed and agility were 3.57 and 3.85 respectively. The required table value was 2.14 for the degrees of freedom 14 at the 0.05 level of significance. Since the obtained t values were greater than the table value it was found statistically significant.

Table 2 reveals the computation of mean, standard deviation and ‘t’ ratio on speed and agility of control group. The obtained ‘t’ value on speed and agility were 1 and 0.09 respectively. The required table value was 2.14 for the degrees of freedom 14 at the 0.05 level of significance. Since the obtained t values were lesser than the table value it was found statistically insignificant.

Figure 1: Bar Diagram Showing the Mean Value on Speed and Agility of SAQ Training Group (SAQTG) and Control Group (CG)

Discussion on Findings:

The present study indicates that the influence of 12 weeks SAQ training significantly improved the speed and agility of grassroots volleyball players. The results of this study indicated that SAQ training is more efficient to bring out desirable changes over the speed, agility of grassroots volleyball players. The findings of the present study had similarity with the findings of the investigators referred in this study. Speed is one of the basic capabilities' necessary bio motoric in every sport Sukadiyanto et al (2011).The speed is very dependent on power because without power, speed cannot be developed. Agility or agility related to gestures that involve footwork and quick changes of position of the body (Mylsudayu et al., 2015). To be able to provide quality results and quality, one athlete requires agility is good in itself that will affect the performance during exercise so as to improve the performance of athletes. According to Kusnanik et al., (2017) speed and agility can be regarded as the most dominant element in a football game. Some way or method of exercise that can be used to improve the speed and agility of athletes among which the speed ladder run and repeated sprints. Overall running technique can be broken down into several phases, the early phase of the block, the acceleration phase, and the velocity step phase. During the acceleration phase, an athlete increases strides length and step frequency. When an athlete reaches the stage of the maximum constant speed, running speed increased through increased stride length and more importantly through the stride frequency. The speed and acceleration are essentials for football athletes because they need to achieve high speed when chasing a ball in a game of football (Gevat et al., 2012).

Conclusion:

- The conclusion of the present study that the influence of 12 weeks SAQ training significantly improved the speed and agility of grassroots volleyball players.
- It was concluded that this study indicated that SAQ training is more efficient to bring out desirable changes over the speed, agility of grassroots volleyball players.
- It was concluded that the findings of the present study had similarity with the findings of the investigators referred in this study.

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